

Non canonical bases differentially represented in the sex chromosomes of the dioecious plant *Silene latifolia*

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Highlight:

This work shows a differential distribution of oxidized methylcytosines in *Silene latifolia* sex chromosomes, and differential sex specific clustering of selected sex-biased transposable elements and genes based on these modifications.

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Abstract: The oxidation of 5-methylcytosine (5mC) to 5-hydroxymethylcytosine (5hmC), 5-formylcytosine (5fC), and 5-carboxylcytosine (5caC), known as oxi-mCs, garners significant interest in plants as potential epigenetic marks.

While research in mammals has established a role in cell reprogramming, carcinogenesis and gene regulation, their functions in plants remain unclear. In rice, 5hmC has been associated with transposable elements and heterochromatin. This study utilizes *Silene latifolia*, a dioecious plant with heteromorphic sex chromosomes and a genome with a large proportion of transposable elements, which provides a favourable environment for the study of oxi-mCs in individual sexes. Notably, we detected surprisingly high levels of oxi-mCs in *S. latifolia* comparable to mammals. Nuclei showed enrichment in heterochromatic regions, except for 5hmC which signal was homogeneously distributed. Intriguingly, the same X chromosome in females displayed overall enrichment of 5hmC and 5fC regarding its counterpart. This fact is shared with 5mC resembling dosage compensation. Colocalization showed higher correlation between 5mC and 5fC than with 5hmC, suggesting no potential relationship between 5hmC and 5fC. Additionally, the promoter of several sex-linked genes and sex biased TEs gathered on a clear sex-dependent clustering. Together, these findings unveil a hypothetical role of oxi-mCs in *S. latifolia* sex chromosome development, warranting further exploration.

Keywords: *Silene latifolia*, sex chromosomes, transposable elements, cytosine modifications, dosage compensation, oxi-mCs

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Abbreviations:

oxi-mCs: enzymatic oxidation products of 5-methylcytosine

5mC: 5-methylcytosine

5hmC: 5-hydroxymethylcytosine

5fC: 5-formylcytosine

5caC: 5-carboxycytosine

TET: ten-eleven translocation

X_{f1}: female X chromosome number 1

X_{f2}: female X chromosome number 2

X_m: male X chromosome

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Introduction

DNA methylation at the C-5 position of cytosine residue represents one of key processes involved in transposon silencing, development, and transcriptional control of gene expression (Slotkin and Martienssen, 2007; Pikaard and Mittelsten Scheid, 2014; Zhang *et al.*, 2018). In plants, methylated cytosine (5-methylcytosine, 5mC) occurs in all sequence contexts CG, CHG and CHH (Where H represents A, T or C) (Cao and Jacobsen, 2002) and is recognized as the fifth nucleotide base. Plants possess mechanisms for cytosine demethylation. Passive demethylation occurs through reduced or inactive DNA methylation enzymes during replication, which are reduced or inactivated. Meanwhile, active demethylation happens through DNA glycosylase enzymes followed by base excision repair, which then replaces the methylated cytosine for unmethylated (Li *et al.*, 2018). In mammals, three additional intermediates of active demethylation catalyzed by the TET (ten-eleven translocation) family of Fe²⁺- and 2-oxoglutarate-dependent enzymes were discovered. These enzymes convert 5mC to oxidized derivatives (oxi-mCs), namely 5-hydroxymethylcytosine (5hmC), 5-formylcytosine (5fC) and 5-carboxycytosine (5caC) (Tahiliani *et al.*, 2009; He *et al.*, 2011; Pfaffeneder *et al.*, 2011). TET homologues were also confirmed in algae, metazoans, and fungi (Moroz *et al.*, 2014; Zhang *et al.*, 2014; Aravind *et al.*, 2019). It is known that oxi-mCs are not only intermediates of active demethylation, but also these bases are present as stable epigenetic marks (Kriaucionis and Heintz, 2009; Bachman *et al.*, 2015). They are involved in important biological processes ranging from stem cell pluripotency, epigenetic reprogramming, and gene expression to neuron maturation (Wossidlo *et al.*, 2011; Wu *et al.*, 2011; Zhang and Zhou, 2019; Stoyanova *et al.*, 2021). In plants, TET homologues are unidentified but, TET-mediated epimutagenesis of *Arabidopsis thaliana* methylome demonstrated enzymatic machinery able to reduce 5mC from DNA (Ji *et al.*, 2018). Foregoing studies in plants have led to conflicting conclusions, on the one hand with claims of low levels of 5hmC in *A. thaliana* (Erdmann *et al.*, 2015) and on the other hand, demonstrating the presence of all oxi-mCs in different plant species (Tang *et al.*, 2014). Previous research on conifers, which are characterized for possessing large numbers of repetitive sequences, indicates a functional role for cytosine modifications (Yakovlev *et al.*, 2019). It has been shown that oxi-mCs are enriched in the sequence of different transposable elements families and potentially can regulate their activity in mammals and fungi in which they may be important components of centromeres (Chavez *et al.*, 2014; Deniz *et al.*, 2019). Research in rice led to similar findings suggesting a possible role in the regulation of transposable elements by 5-hmC (Wang *et al.*, 2015). Transposable elements (TEs), comprising large portions of plant genomes, exhibit significant variation in copy number and distribution across species (Kejnovsky *et al.*, 2012). Repetitive DNA accumulation has an important role in sex chromosome evolution and epigenetics (Kejnovsky *et al.*, 2009; Hobza *et al.*, 2015, 2017). In melon, a plant without sex chromosomes but with sex determination genes, an insertion of the hAT DNA transposon triggers the methylation of the transcription factor CMWIP1 leading to gynoecey (Martin *et al.*, 2009).

Silene latifolia is a dioecious plant with cytologically well distinguishable heteromorphic sex chromosomes ((Kejnovsky and Vyskot, 2010). In the X:Y system present in *S. latifolia*, the lack of recombination in the sex specific region of the Y chromosome leads to an accumulation of deleterious mutations and degeneration originating two different evolutionary strata (Bergero *et al.*, 2007). However, not only gene degeneration but also DNA rearrangements and the gathering of satellites, microsatellites, plastid sequences and transposons in sex chromosomes is broadly documented, and specific repetitive sequences can also be differentially found between X and Y chromosomes (Hobza *et al.*, 2006; Cermak *et al.*, 2008; Puterova *et al.*, 2018). This abundance of transposable elements (TEs) in plants with heteromorphic sex chromosomes presents a compelling opportunity to investigate the presence and distribution of oxi-mCs in individual sexes (Hobza *et al.*, 2017). The present study is aimed to profile the global levels of three oxi-mCs in both sexes of *S. latifolia*, visualize their distribution and describe the global pattern in interphase nuclei and metaphase chromosomes and finally, investigate a potential relationship of sex biased genes and TE clusters with oxi-mCs.

Material and methods

Plant material

This study employed a well-established inbred population (U17, 17 generations of full-sib mating) of both male and female *S. latifolia* specimens obtained from the Institute of Biophysics collection in Brno, Czech Republic. The plants were cultivated under controlled greenhouse conditions, following a standard long-day photoperiod (22°C, 16 hours light/8 hours dark). For DNA immunoprecipitation and subsequent 2D-UPLC-MS/MS analysis, genomic DNA was isolated from young leaves in a vegetative state (approximately 1 month old) using a rapid nitrogen flash-freezing technique. Metaphase chromosomes and interphase nuclei, required for immunostaining, were obtained from synchronized root tips following the protocol outlined by (Lengerova *et al.*, 2004).

DNA immunoprecipitation

DNA was extracted using NucleoSpin® Plant II DNA Kit (Macherey Nagel, Düren, Germany) according to manufacturer instructions. DNA immunoprecipitation assay (DIP) was performed according to (Rodríguez Lorenzo *et al.*, 2020). Antibodies used in DIP were, anti 5-mC (Abcam, cat. nr. ab214727), anti 5-hmC (Abcam, cat. nr. ab214728), anti 5-fC (Diagenode, cat. nr.C15310200) and anti 5-caC (Diagenode, cat. nr. C15410204-100). Genomic DNA (20 µg) was diluted in 450 µL 1x IP buffer (10 mM Na₃PO₄ pH 7.0, 140 mM NaCl and 0.05 % Triton X-100). A total of 7 pulses of 90 % intensity for 15 s for each sample at 4 °C were delivered with an ultrasonic processor UP50H (Hielscher Ultrasonics GmbH, Teltow, Germany). The size of the sonicated DNA was verified on a 2 % agarose gel with an average size of 400 bp and a range of from 200 to 800 bp. DNA was aliquoted to three 1.5 mL DNA LoBind® Tubes (Eppendorf-5 Prime, Inc., Boulder, CO, USA) to avoid sample surface binding. Samples were heat denatured at 95 °C for 10 min and then immediately cooled on ice for 10 min. 7 µg of antibody was added and samples were incubated on a

rotating platform overnight at 4 °C. DIP was performed using 50 µL of Invitrogen Protein G or A Dynabeads and incubated 2h on a rotating platform at 4 °C. Samples were three times washed with 1x IP buffer using a magnetic rack and suspended in digestion buffer (50 mM Tris pH 8, 10 mM EDTA, 0.5% SDS) with 1µL of 20 mg/mL proteinase K and incubated for 1 h at 50 °C on a rotating platform. Untreated sonicated genomic DNA was processed in parallel and considered as the input sample. Precipitated DNA was recovered using MinElute PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen). Once the DNA was purified and quantified, we proceeded with qPCR.

DIP-qPCR

Quantitative PCR of immunoprecipitated DNA was performed as follows: 10 ng of input DNA used as a normalization control or immunoprecipitated DNA, 5 µM of each primer and SensiFAST HRM Kit (Bioline Reagents Ltd., London, UK) were mixed according to manufacturer's instructions and amplified using the Rotor-Gene Q (Qiagen, Dusseldorf, Germany) according to the program 95°C for 3 min, 40 cycles at 95°C for 5 seconds and 60°C for 30 seconds. A latter melting step from 30°C to 95°C was carried out to test product specificity. The promoter region from each gene (500 bp upstream from transcription starting site) was selected for amplification analysis. Four replicates for each transcript from a pool of individuals were analyzed using the LinReg software (Ruijter *et al.*, 2009) (Primer sequences are indicated in Supplementary Table S1. The data for the analysis was obtained from the enrichment ratio according to the formula $\text{IP DNA}/\text{IN DNA}$ (IP DNA: Immunoprecipitated DNA, IN DNA: Input DNA) coming out of the qPCR results. An internal standard control with a known sequence was included in the experiment. The binary vector pCAMBIA-2301 and the primers F: ACGTAAGGGATGACGCACA and R: CGCGATCCAGACTGAATGCC were used to generate an amplicon of 389bp. In the PCR, for each reaction cytidine was replaced with the corresponding modified nucleoside: 5-Methyl-2'-deoxycytidine, 5-Hydroxy-2'-deoxycytidine, 5-Formyl-2'-deoxycytidine and 5-Carboxy-2'-deoxycytidine (TriLink BioTechnologies Inc., San Diego, CA, USA). The reaction was as follows: Buffer 5X we added 10 µL; dNTP (10 µM) we added 5 µL; Q5 High Fidelity DNA Polymerase (New England Biolabs. Inc., Beverly, MA, USA) we added 1 µL; primers F+R (10 µM each) we added 2 µL; DNA (1 ng/µL) we added 2 µL; a final volume up to 50 µL of ddH₂O was added to the reaction. The program used was: 98°C for 30 seconds and 35 cycles at 98°C for 10 seconds, 55°C for 30 seconds and 72°C for 30 seconds. A final extension step at 72°C for 2 minutes was included. The IP DNA/IN DNA ratio for each cytosine modification is presented in Supplementary Figure S1. Three replicates for each immunoprecipitation were analyzed using the LinReg software (Ruijter *et al.*, 2009)

Statistical analysis

For the data analysis, Kruskal-Wallis test was applied for the comparison of global quantification. Euclidean distance was used for the clustering analysis from immunoprecipitation data. Finally, t-test was employed for image analysis comparison between both X chromosomes in female and male plants of *S. latifolia* for 5hmC and 5fC signal. The data for this analysis was the ratio Antibody signal/DAPI signal mean values. For

all the statistical tests, a minimum of three replicates were used. Statistical analysis was done in (RStudio Team, 2022).

Slide preparation and immunostaining

Slide preparations were carried out according to (Houben *et al.*, 2003) with modifications. Immunostaining was performed using following the procedure: slides were fixed in 4% formaldehyde in PBS for 10 min and subsequently washed three times in PBS. Samples were denatured in 2M HCl for 15 min at room temperature and washed three times in PBS. Blocking was performed in a 3% blocking buffer (3% BSA (w/v), 0.1% Tween20 in 1× PBS) at 37 °C for 60 min and followed by incubation at 4 °C overnight with primary antibody diluted in 1% blocking solution (1% BSA (w/v), 0.1% Tween 20 in 1 × PBS). The primary antibodies used in this study included rabbit anti-5mC (1:1000, Abcam, cat. nr. ab214727), mouse anti-5mC (1:1000, Diagenode cat. nr. C15200003), rabbit anti-5hmC (1:200, Abcam, cat. nr. ab 214728), rabbit anti-5fC (1:200, Active Motif, cat. nr. 61223) and rabbit anti-5caC (1:100, Diagenode, cat. nr. C15410204-100). After several washes in 1× PBS, the slides were incubated with secondary antibody diluted in 1% blocking solution (1% BSA (w/v), 0.1% Tween 20 in 1 × PBS) at room temperature for 1 h. The secondary antibodies included Fluorescein (FITC) AffiniPure Fab Fragment Donkey Anti-Mouse IgG (H+L) (1:400, JacksonImmunoResearch, cat. nr. AB_2340797) and CyTM3 AffiniPure Fab Fragment Goat Anti-Rabbit IgG (H+L) (1:400, JacksonImmunoResearch, cat. nr. AB_2313593). In double immunostaining experiments (5mC+5hmC and 5mC+5fC) the two primary or secondary antibodies were incubated together. After secondary antibody incubation slides were washed three times for 10 min in PBS, dehydrated in ethanol series and mounted in Vectashield containing DAPI (Vector Laboratories, cat. nr. GZ-93952-27). A negative control was included for all antibodies (Supplementary Figure S2).

Image acquisition and processing

Fluorescence images were taken in super resolution mode on inverted microscope Zeiss Axio Observer.7 with laser scanning unit LSM 880 and Airyscan detector. The Plan-Apochromat 63x/1.4 Oil DIC M27 objective was used for all imaging. Fluorescence signals were recorded appropriate laser excitations: for DAPI, 405nm and Cy3, 561nm. Images were taken using Monochromatic camera Axiocam MRm driven by ZEN Black software. Recorded Airyscan super-resolution images were analyzed by Zen Blue software (version 3.0) and images were deconvoluted using Airyscan Joint Deconvolution function and 3D reconstructions were produced using Imaris software (version 9.3, Bitplane, Zurich, Switzerland). Image quantification for DAPI and antibody signal was performed using Fiji (Schindelin *et al.*, 2012). The whole chromosome length and width from the maximum projection was used for the measurements and statistical analysis. The plugin Color profiler was used to split the RGB channels and calculate both, the mean values for the global image analysis and the data for the graphical signal distribution in the sex chromosomes. The selected sex chromosome pairs in Figures 4 and 5 came from the same metaphase in females. For males, not all the images came from the same metaphase, and all the figures used for the artwork can be found in Supplementary Figure S3-S6 and in data availability section.

Quantification of 5mC and oxi-mCs in DNA.

Genomic content of C-5 modified nucleobases was determined by quantitative analysis of the corresponding deoxynucleosides after enzymatic hydrolysis of DNA performed using a modified method described by (Starczak *et al.*, 2021). Briefly, DNA samples were completely dried in SpeedVac system. Next, the pellet was dissolved in 50 μ L of MilliQ-grade deionized water and mixed with 50 μ L of NP1 buffer (200 mM ammonium acetate, 0.2 mM ZnCl₂; pH 4.6). Nuclease P1 (100 U, New England Biolabs) and tetrahydrouridine (10 mg/ml) were added to the mixture and incubated at 37°C overnight. Subsequently, 13 μ L of 10% (v/v) NH₄OH and 12 U of Shrimp Alkaline Phosphatase (rSAP, New England Biolabs) were added to each sample following 2 h incubation at 37 °C. All hydrolysates were ultrafiltered prior to injection and concentrated in SpeedVac to a final volume of 10 μ L.

DNA hydrolysates were spiked with a solution of internal standard in volumetric ratio 4:1, to concentration of 50 fmol/ μ L of [D₃]-5-(hydroxymethyl)-2'-deoxycytidine (5hmdC), [¹³C₁₀, ¹⁵N₂]-5-formyl-2'-deoxycytidine (5fdC), [¹³C₁₀, ¹⁵N₂]-5-carboxy-2'-deoxycytidine (5-cadC), and analyzed using isotope-dilution automated online two-dimensional ultra-performance liquid chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry and UV detection (2D-UPLC-MS/MS).

Chromatographic separation was performed in 2D-UPLC system with photo-diode array detector for the first dimension chromatography (used for the quantification of canonical deoxynucleosides) and tandem quadrupole mass spectrometer (Xevo TQ-XS, Waters), using columns: Waters Cortecs T3 column (150 mm×3 mm, 1.6 μ m) with a precolumn at the first dimension, a Waters X-select C18 CSH (100 mm×2.1 mm, 1.7 μ m) at the second dimension and Waters X-select C18 CSH (20 mm×3 mm, 3.5 μ m) as a trap/transfer column. At the first dimension was applied flow rate 0.5 mL/min, injection volume 2 μ L and gradient elution for 10 min using a mobile phase 0.05 % acetate (A) and acetonitrile (B) (0.7-5 % B for 5 min, followed by the column washing with 30 % acetonitrile and re-equilibration with 99.3 % A for 3.6 min). At the second dimension the flow rate was 0.35 mL/min in a gradient elution for 10 min using a mobile phase 0.01 % acetate (A) and methanol (B) (1-50 % B for 4 min, isocratic flow of 50 % B for 1.5 min, and re-equilibration with 99 % A up to the next injection).

All the samples were analyzed in three to five technical replicates and the technical mean was used for further calculation. Transition patterns for all the analyzed compounds along with specific detector settings are given in the Supplementary Table S2. The quantities of canonical deoxynucleosides were determined by UV detection at 260 nm for 2'-deoxythymidine (dT), and at 280 nm for 2'-deoxyguanosine (dG) and 5-methyl-2'-deoxycytidine. Total deoxynucleosides amount (dN) calculated as doubled sum of dT and dG was used as a reference for quantitative expression of modified ones.

Results

Global levels of cytosine modifications showed variation however, the sex was not the variable

The first experimental approach was global quantification analysis for all the cytosine modifications in the genomic DNA of *S. latifolia* male and female plants. The most abundant cytosine modification was 5mC, with a median value of 59.61 modifications for males and 61.90 modifications for females per kilobase Figure 1. For the oxidative forms 5hmC and 5fC the levels were three orders of magnitude less, and 5caC presented six orders of magnitude less than 5mC. The statistical analysis did not show significant differences between male and female plants for any of the modifications under analysis.

5mC, 5fC and 5caC are preferentially localized in DAPI dense regions in contrast to 5hmC

The fluorescence signal pattern in the different nuclei presented in Figure 2 and 3, clearly demonstrates colocalization of 5mC, 5fC and 5caC with DAPI dense territories in both sexes, which are usually considered as heterochromatin-related regions. Forementioned 5hmC signal was distributed throughout the nuclei on the other hand, and appeared to be present in small uniform size speckles in both sexes. The same signal pattern was observed in metaphase chromosomes in both sexes (Supplementary Figure S3-S6).

A differential distribution on one of the X chromosomes in females depends on 5mC, 5hmC and 5fC

We set a nomenclature to distinguish among X sex chromosomes: X_{f1} ; X chromosome from females 1, X_{f2} : X chromosome from females 2 and X_m : X chromosome from males. In all situations, X_{f1} was the chromosome with higher 5mC signal. Fluorescence, for all the antibodies except that against 5caC, the chromosome X_{f2} showed less signal than its counterpart X_{f1} (Figure 4). The X_{f2} has arms displayed higher intensity in 5mC and 5hmC. For 5fC, however, the long arm has the higher intensity signal. Based on the total antibody/DAPI ratio for X chromosomes, differences (t-test; p-value < 0.05) were found between both chromosomes for 5mC, 5hmC and 5fC. Differences were not observed between X_m and Y chromosomes, or between X_{f1} and X_{f2} compared to X_m . As one X in females, X_m displayed the same differential staining along the chromosome, finding differences between both arms. In this chromosome 5mC and 5fC signal was mostly localized in the short arm while 5hmC had an opposite trend. An association for both X chromosomes in females with 5hmC or 5fC compared to 5mC, revealed in all cases that X_{f1} was the chromosome with higher signal (Figure 5A, 5B, 5C and 5D). According to the observations made on the associated fluorescence graphs in Figure 5A and 5B, both antibody signals had a similar pattern for 5mC-5fC. However, for 5mC-5hmC the pattern was different. Colocalization analysis detect differences between 5hmC and 5fC colocalization with 5mC (Figure 5E). This difference is always present regardless the chromosome and the sex, and higher colocalization for 5mC and 5fC. A clustering analysis groups each female X chromosome differently with the two sex chromosomes in males (Figure 5F). It is based on 5hmC or 5fC,

but both oxi-mCs display higher signal on chromosome X_{f1} . Which could indicate a common association of chromosome X_{f2} based on 5hmC together with chromosomes X_m and Y. On the other hand, the clustering of chromosomes X_{f1} , X_m and Y may indicate a common connection dependent on the combination of 5fC and 5mC.

Selected sex-linked genes and bias-represented TEs are clustered according to oxi-mCs

The promoter regions for the X and Y alleles from the genes *SIAP3*; *SIDD44*; *SI3*; *SI4*; *SI7* and *SISs* are already involved in epigenetic regulation and were investigated in this work (Rodríguez Lorenzo *et al.*, 2018, 2020). The selection of the sex biased-represented TEs was according to (Cermak *et al.*, 2008; Kubat *et al.*, 2008; Kralova *et al.*, 2014; Puterova *et al.*, 2018), and the selected TEs were: *Tekay Cl. 4*, *Angela Cl. 7* and *Cl. 1*, *Retand Cl. 9*, *Athila Cl. 10* and *Cl. 3*, and *Ogre Cl. 5*, *Cl. 6* and *Cl. 11*. For this analysis the enrichment raw data of 5mC antibody from (Rodríguez Lorenzo *et al.*, 2018) was included. TE clusters show common clustering based on sex, indicating a different regulation in males and females (Figure 6A). The grouping suggests that females are linked to 5hmC and 5caC. Athila Cl 10 tested in females has its own branch and it is connected to 5mC and 5fC. In Figure 6B, the different alleles in the dendrogram gather distinguishing between X and Y chromosome in males. This clustering is also kept for Strata. In the differential clustering between X and Y alleles in males, the X alleles in females share the same position in the branch. This finding, independently of the parent, may indicate a connection among all X alleles based on the oxi-mCs and a different behavior for the Y alleles. In addition, this connection is extended in the strata I (older) and II (younger) of the Y chromosome. The results suggest that alleles from the Y chromosome belonging to stratum I could be mainly associated to 5mC. The alleles *SI3X* and *SI7X* tested in females clustered in an independent branch. These alleles show high levels for all the modifications however, they are gathered to 5fC and 5caC.

The clustering according to the oxi-mCs reflects differences in both dendrograms, indicating a different relationship between genes and TEs. For TEs, 5mC clusters with 5fC meanwhile 5hmC clusters with 5caC. For genes, 5fC and 5caC cluster together and, 5mC and 5hmC remain single. This differential clustering may indicate sex dependent connection for TEs and chromosome dependent connection for genes.

Discussion

Despite oxi-mCs are the less represented compared to other cytosine modifications, we were able to detect 5caC in genomic DNA. A study in Norway spruce failed to detect 5caC using the same methodology (Yakovlev *et al.*, 2019). One possible explanation could be that the levels of 5mC in *S. latifolia* are from 2 to 3 times higher, and the levels of oxi-mCs were 10 times higher. Because levels of oxi-mCs are connected to the levels of DNA methylation, the elevated levels of all 5mC precursors can be a consequence of active DNA demethylation. These results agree with the findings reported previously by (Tang *et al.*, 2014), showing similar levels of 5fC and 5caC in a number of plant species. Moreover, in the fungus *Coprinopsis cinerea* a bias for 5fC production at the expense of other oxi-mCs has been shown (Zhang *et al.*, 2014). Comparing our global oxi-mCs levels with data from previous studies, it is important to point out that the presented results from tandem mass spectrometry

are even higher than levels reported in different mammal tissues, where their biological function was directly described (Wu *et al.*, 2011; Gackowski *et al.*, 2015; Wu and Zhang, 2017). For *S. latifolia*, our main goal was not only to see the differences between the sexes, but also to show the signal distribution in interphase nuclei and metaphase chromosomes, especially in the sex chromosomes. Colocalization of 5mC with DAPI dense foci was expected according to (Tariq *et al.*, 2003). These foci are considered to be heterochromatin-linked with a dominant contribution in repetitive DNA (Fransz *et al.*, 2002). Despite 5fC and 5caC followed the same trend, the distribution of 5hmC was different. A dispersed signal throughout the nuclei with a spotted signal pattern indicated the presence in euchromatic regions. Potentially, this difference could reflect a difference in the function of 5hmC which is in agreement with the same observations reported in mammal embryonic stem cells (Szulwach *et al.*, 2011; Kubiura *et al.*, 2012).

Previous studies suggested the evolution of partial dosage compensation in *S. latifolia*, (Muyle *et al.*, 2012, 2018; Krasovec *et al.*, 2019) and reviewed in (Muyle *et al.*, 2022). Cytological experiments carried in *S. latifolia* have proved that one X chromosome is enriched in histone repressive marks, 5mC and is late replicating (Siroky *et al.*, 1998; Bačovský *et al.*, 2019). The 5mC observations agree with previous studies and additionally, we found that 5hmC and 5fC selectively mark the same X chromosome. It is worth noting that a biased distribution of 5hmC has also been observed between X chromosomes in mice (Bogomazova *et al.*, 2014). On the other hand, in this work, the positively stained X chromosome was associated with the active status and an accumulating 5hmC signal has been described during the silent X chromosome reactivation. During our study it was also observed that sister chromatids in the metaphase occasionally stained differentially for oxi-mCs, and this was random and not specific to any chromosome. These observations are consistent with those from (Kubiura *et al.*, 2012; Bogomazova *et al.*, 2014). The authors explained this phenomenon as a possible process of cumulative conversion between oxi-mCs. Published work on plants links 5hmC with silent TEs (Wang *et al.*, 2015), and in mammals is connected to Embryonic Stem Cells and is inversely correlated to cell differentiation (Deniz *et al.*, 2019). On the other hand, for 5fC it is associated to hypomethylation and gene expression and to transposon activation in oocytes (Inoue *et al.*, 2012; Raiber *et al.*, 2012; Neri *et al.*, 2015). Our data suggest a common behavior for 5mC and 5fC that could be interpreted as silencing if we look at the main function of methylation, and it is supported by transposon silencing in fungi (Ličytè *et al.*, 2022). Likewise, the low correlation between 5hmC and 5mC agrees with a previous research published in rye (Kalinka *et al.*, 2023). This aspect might indicate that 5hmC could have a dual activation/repression role. However, this fact remains to be seen through global genomic analysis of chemically modified DNA to identify the cytosine context.

Working with *S. latifolia* offered the possibility to include in this work both, sex biased-represented TEs and selected sex-linked genes. The epigenetic regulation of these genes in previous analyses involving DNA methylation and histone modifications detected differences between X and Y alleles and was one of the reasons for the inclusion (Rodríguez Lorenzo *et al.*, 2018, 2020). The second was the degree of degeneration these genes have (Marais *et al.*, 2008), including mutations and substitutions. Bolstering their inclusion in this investigation, a specific gene regulation by 5hmC based on preventing spurious transcription has been reported in humans (Pfeifer, 2023; Wu *et al.*, 2023). Based on the degeneration of these

genes, 5hmC might have a role in the fidelity of gene transcription and could be the cause for the difference found in *S17* and *SISs* promoters between X and Y alleles. Additionally, the fact that several Y allele promoters and introns have increased in length compared to the X alleles due to transposable-element accumulation, offers an opportunity for differential regulation analysis (Marais *et al.*, 2008; Blavet *et al.*, 2015). This fact opens the gate to other options nonetheless. In fungi, there are lineage-specific expansions with numerous TET/JBP genes, which are often associated with a unique class of transposable elements (Iyer *et al.*, 2014). It has been reported a previous accumulation of repetitive DNA before gene degeneration (Kubat *et al.*, 2008), and a possible sex specific transposon silencing (Puterova *et al.*, 2018). Epigenetic silencing is the main mechanism to regulate sex biased-represented TEs in *S. latifolia* (Kubat *et al.*, 2014), and 5hmC has been linked to silent TEs and genes in rice (Wang *et al.*, 2015). In this work, we show sex specific TE clustering based on the oxi-mCs enrichment. Given specific sex biased TE clusters, which are linked to sex chromosome evolution and the reality that no information is available for plant TET/JBP genes, all the possibilities should be taken into account. In fungi there is evidence for the association of TET/JBP genes to transposons (Iyer *et al.*, 2014) and in mouse embryonic stem cells, different TET bind different TE classes, finding 5hmC linked to LINE-1 elements (De La Rica *et al.*, 2016). The sex clustering is not as clear in genes as it is in TEs, but the clustering gathers the majority of X alleles from females and from males apart from the Y allele in males. It is crucial to remember X chromosomes recombine opposite to Y chromosome (Zluvova *et al.*, 2007). In the same way, the Y alleles from males clustered in stratum I linked to 5mC and different histone modifications, all of them repressive marks associated to genes in the Y chromosome (Rodríguez Lorenzo *et al.*, 2018, 2020). The clustering according to the oxi-mCs reflects differences in both dendrograms, indicating different association between genes and TEs. For TEs, 5mC clusters with 5fC meanwhile 5hmC clusters with 5caC. This finding aligns with the strong correlation observed in the double immunohistochemistry, not only in the sex chromosomes, but also in the autosomes (See Supplementary Figures S5-S6).

The intricate interplay between epigenetic modifications and sex chromosome evolution remains a fascinating subject of investigation. Three key milestones mark this process: sex determination, dosage compensation, and Y chromosome degeneration.) In *S. latifolia*, we can find evidence narrowing down a possible epigenetic regulation for all of them (Muyle *et al.*, 2018; Rodríguez Lorenzo *et al.*, 2018, 2020; Bačovský *et al.*, 2022; Akagi *et al.*, 2023) and this study provides evidence of a connection for oxi-mCs in female sex chromosome evolution and Y chromosome degeneration, paving the way for further research to elucidate a hypothetical specific function in this ideal plant model for oxi-mCs analysis.

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Figure legends

Figure 1: Boxplot graphical representation of 5mC, 5hmC, 5fC and 5caC global content in *S. latifolia* female and male leaves. The box represents the interquartile range (IQR) defined as the range between Q3-Q1. The line inside the box represents the median. The whiskers represent the most extreme data within the distribution. Individual data beyond the whiskers is considered as an outlier. n = 4, Black dots represent individual data points. Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 2: Immunodetection of oxi-mCs in *S. latifolia* male. The nuclei (DAPI) are present in blue and signals of oxi-mCs are represented in red (ANTIBODY). The bar represents 10 μ m.

Figure 3: Immunodetection of oxi-mCs in *S. latifolia* female. The nuclei (DAPI) are present in blue and signals of oxi-mCs are represented in red (ANTIBODY). The bar represents 10 μ m.

Figure 4: Magnification detail of 5mC, 5hmC, 5fC and 5caC immunolocalization in metaphasic *Silene latifolia* female X chromosomes and male X and Y chromosomes stained with

DAPI. A graph for the associated fluorescence along each chromosome length for antibody vs DAPI signals is shown on the left of the chromosome images. The relative antibody/DAPI mean fluorescence ratio for both X sex chromosomes in females and X and Y chromosomes in males is shown on the right of the chromosome images. For all the bar plots n = 3. Black dots represent individual data points. Asterisks represent t-test p-value (* = $p < 0.05$).

Figure 5: A: Magnification detail of 5mC-5hmC and 5mC-5fC colocalization output in metaphasic *Silene latifolia* female X chromosomes. A graph for the associated fluorescence along each chromosome length for each antibody combination is shown on the left of the chromosome images. B: Normalized antibody/DAPI mean fluorescence ratio for both X sex chromosomes for the antibody combination 5mC-5hmC and 5mC-5fC, and Pearson mean correlation for each combination correlation. For all the bar plots n = 4. Black dots represent individual data points. Asterisks represent t-test p-value (* = $p < 0.05$, ** = $p < 0.01$).

Figure 6: Distance matrix from the enrichment of oxi-mCs performed on male and female *S. latifolia* plants represented by a heatmap and the associated dendrogram. A: Data from immunoprecipitation for sex biased-represented TE clusters. Additional annotation includes Sex, TE family and Bias representation. Bias labelling code: X \uparrow ; overrepresented in X chromosome, X \downarrow ; underrepresented in X chromosome, X \equiv ; no changes in X chromosome, Y \uparrow ; overrepresented in Y chromosome, Y \downarrow ; underrepresented in Y chromosome. For each TE cluster a combination of one X and one Y situation is applied. B: Data from immunoprecipitation includes X and Y alleles from selected sex-linked genes. Additional annotation for Sex and Strata is included. Sex labelling code: F; both X alleles in female plants, XM; X allele in male plants, YM; Y allele in male plants.

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Figure 2: Immunodetection of oxo-mCs in *S. latifolia* male. The nuclei (DAPI) are present in blue and signals of oxo-mCs are represented in red (ANTIBODY). The bar represents 10 μ m.

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